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D1.2 First version of Ethics and Safety Manual

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Abbreviations

CE	Conformité Européenne
CEN	Comité Européen de Normalisation
CENELEC	European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization
CIOMS	Council of International Organizations of Medical Sciences
CPP	Comités de protection des personnes
CRO	Clinical Research Organization
DMP	Data Management Plan
DPO	Data Protection Officer
EC	European Commission
eCF	electronic Consent Form
ECHR	European Convention on Human Rights
EDPS	European Data Protection Supervisor
ECG	Electrocardiography
EEA	Extended European Area
EEG	Electroencephalography
eiDAS	Electronic Identification, Authentication and trusted Services
eIC	electronic informed consent
EMG	Electromyography
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
EU	European Union
EUCROF	European CRO Federation
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GHTF	Global Harmonization Task Force
H2020	Horizon 2020 Program of the European Commission
HIPAA	Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act

JRA	Joint Research Activities
MDR	Medical Devices Regulations
PI	Principle Investigator
QoL	Quality of Life
REBs	Research Ethics Boards
REC	Research Ethic Committee
TCPS	Tri-Council Policy Statement Ethical Conduct For Research Involving Humans
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
VR	Virtual Reality
WHO	World Health Organization
WMA	World Medical Association
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

During its life, the VITALISE project will encapsulate multimodal data collection phases towards the development and evaluation of novel supportive interventions related to rehabilitation, transitional care, and everyday living environments. As the corner stone of these data collection phases are the individuals that will provide the data, special attention will be given on the compliance of the collection processes with ethical regulations and guidelines on research involving human beings, as well as on the safety of the sensors, tools, and devices involved and the protection of personal and health data.

To this end, the present deliverable "D1.2 First version of ethics and safety manual" constitutes a reference guide for the VITALISE investigators by reporting on the international, European and National ethical regulations, device safety standards and certifications, as well as accepted data management procedures. Moreover, this deliverable presents a first plan for the VITALISE scheduled data collection to be compliant with the reported regulations and guidelines and evaluates potential concerns early in order to be mitigated effectively, through the proper management of ethical and data handling-related issues.

1 Introduction

1.1 The VITALISE Project

Researchers in the Health and Wellbeing domain need 1) convenient access to research infrastructures, 2) direct engagement of people in order to validate hypotheses, co-design solutions and services, evaluate their feasibility and effectiveness and participate in the translation and mobilization of outcomes and 3) experience from multidisciplinary domains (e.g. healthcare management, assistive technologies, data science) to deal with the complexity of health and wellbeing research.

Over the last few years, Living Labs have emerged as resilient research and innovation infrastructures and have proved to be key to the integration of research and innovation processes in real life settings, focusing primarily on people and their engagement in research procedures. VITALISE opens up Living Lab Infrastructures as a means to facilitate and promote research activities in the Health and Wellbeing domain in Europe and beyond by enabling in person Transnational Access to 17 Living Lab research infrastructures and by supporting remote digital access to datasets (Virtual Access) of rehabilitation, transitional care and everyday life activities through harmonized processes and common tools. VITALISE will design and develop ICT tools for shared access of similar devices and applications used across Living Labs, as well as for collecting, storing and sharing datasets. Lastly, VITALISE will invest in the development of Training methods towards the wider understanding and valorisation of Living Lab methodologies in the research community.

1.2 Relevant Project Aspect

Within the VITALISE project, three Joint Research Activities (JRAs) are planned in WP5, WP6 and WP7, with data collection executed in tandem for the 3 JRAs. The datasets that will be generated/collected in the lifecycle of the VITALISE project subtend to fields of: (a) rehabilitation supported by technology, where data regarding dual mobility, and biosignal monitoring, quality of life (QoL) and physical assessments will be produced (WP5, Task 5.4); (b) transitional care, where data related to patient mobility and functionality, biosignal monitoring, emotional detection from patient monitoring tools will be produced (WP6, Task 6.4); (c) everyday living environments, where data concerning human activity (start, duration, frequency of exercise, routines, habits, and social participation) will be produced (WP7, Task 7.4). Data collection in each WP is heralded by small-scale pilot data collection (Tasks 5.3, 6.3, 7.3, respectively) to test for functionality, deployment, usability and feasibility issues accompanied by the evaluation of each intervention.

One of the main goals of the ongoing Task 1.4 - Ethical and Security Management is to evaluate the ethical feasibility and safety of the planned JRAs and their interventions, the respective data collection, based on the ethical, safety and data protection requirements of the respective host countries which the JRAs will take place. Additionally, in Task 1.4 the sensors, tools and devices will be evaluated, and the level of concern will be determined. It will also develop the consortium approach complying to different ethical standards and identify all ethical aspects that could be affected by the project and ensure that VITALISE is executed accordingly. The products of Task 1.4 will be a first version of the ethics and safety manual (present report) on month 6 of the project and prior to the beginning of all data collection phases and a final version of it on month 24, when all data collection phases will be unfolding.

1.3 Purpose of Document

The purpose of Deliverable D1.2 - *First version of ethics and safety manual* is to constitute an initial version of a reference guide for the VITALISE researchers by reporting on the relevant, both national and international, ethical regulations, devices safety standards and certifications, as well as proper data management procedures. Furthermore, this deliverable presents an early plan for the VITALISE data collection to be ethically compliant, identifies potential concerns and evaluates their importance and effect, in order to mitigate them as early as possible in the project's life. The deliverable ends

with the established VITALISE procedures regarding ethical and legal compliance, and data handling are presented. As this is a public report, it can additionally be used as a reference guide for other researchers.

Task 1.4 is continuous throughout the project and as such, ethical, safety and data management procedures reported in this deliverable are subject to change based on the review of the JRAs research protocols by the relevant authorities. Their final versions will be presented in D1.3 - *Final version of ethics and safety manual* (M24).

1.4 Document Structure

The deliverable is structured as such:

- **Section 1** (this sections) provides information regarding the VITALISE project, aspects related to it, and the purpose of the document;
- **Section 2** outlines the International, European and National ethical guidelines and regulations that will be followed in the lifecycle of the VITALISE project. Additionally, it presents information concerning the electronic informed consent that will be used in the premises of the project;
- **Section 3** describes the regulations and directives related to the safety of medical devices, emphasizing on their main standards and certifications;
- **Section 4** addresses data management regulations regarding data protection, exchange, access, as well as good practices on the use and dissemination of data. Additionally, it outlines the VITALISE project's compliance with research ethics and device safety during the three JRAs and open calls for researchers, and details the general management procedures in case of adverse events. Finally, it presents the VITALISE project's compliance with the previously mentioned data protection regulations (Sections 4);
- **Section 5** provides an overview regarding the framework for managing ethical in the duration of the VITALISE project;
- **Section 6** includes the references for this deliverable;
- **Section 7** contains a generic consent form adapted to suit the purposes of the VITALISE project (Appendix 1).

2 Ethical Regulations and Guidelines

2.1 International ethical guidelines

This section summarises international ethical regulations and guidelines relevant to research involving human subjects.

2.1.1 Declaration of Helsinki

The World Medical Association (WMA) Declaration of Helsinki (World Medical Association, 2013) constitutes a statement on ethical guidelines regarding medical research that involves humans. The key relevant articles of the Declaration of Helsinki (World Medical Association, 2013) to VITALISE are summarised below:

General principles

1. It is the duty of the physician to promote and safeguard the health, well-being and rights of patients, including those who are involved in medical research. The physician's knowledge and conscience are dedicated to the fulfilment of this duty.
2. Medical progress is based on research that ultimately must include studies involving human subjects. The primary purpose of medical research involving human subjects is to understand the causes, development and effects of diseases and improve preventive, diagnostic and therapeutic interventions (methods, procedures and treatments). Even the best proven interventions must be evaluated continually through research for their safety, effectiveness,

- efficiency, accessibility and quality. Medical research is subject to ethical standards that promote and ensure respect for all human subjects and protect their health and rights.
3. While the primary purpose of medical research is to generate new knowledge, this goal can never take precedence over the rights and interests of individual research subjects. It is the duty of physicians who are involved in medical research to protect the life, health, dignity, integrity, right to self-determination, privacy, and confidentiality of personal information of research subjects. The responsibility for the protection of research subjects must always rest with the physician or other health care professionals and never with the research subjects, even though they have given consent.
 4. Physicians must consider the ethical, legal and regulatory norms and standards for research involving human subjects in their own countries as well as applicable international norms and standards. No national or international ethical, legal or regulatory requirement should reduce or eliminate any of the protections for research subjects set forth in this Declaration.
 5. Medical research involving human subjects must be conducted only by individuals with the appropriate ethics and scientific education, training and qualifications. Research on patients or healthy volunteers requires the supervision of a competent and appropriately qualified physician or other health care professional.
 6. Physicians who combine medical research with medical care should involve their patients in research only to the extent that this is justified by its potential preventive, diagnostic or therapeutic value and if the physician has good reason to believe that participation in the research study will not adversely affect the health of the patients who serve as research subjects.
 7. Appropriate compensation and treatment for subjects who are harmed as a result of participating in research must be ensured.

Vulnerable Groups and Individuals

8. Some groups and individuals are particularly vulnerable and may have an increased likelihood of being wronged or of incurring additional harm. As such, All vulnerable groups and individuals should receive specifically considered protection.
9. Medical research with a vulnerable group is only justified if the research is responsive to the health needs or priorities of this group and the research cannot be carried out in a non-vulnerable group. In addition, this group should stand to benefit from the knowledge, practices or interventions that result from the research.

Risks, burdens and benefits

10. Most interventions involve risks. As a result, medical research must only be conducted when the importance of the objectives outweighs the underlying risks. Researchers must *a priori* define the risks arising from the research and take mitigation measures. Additionally, if there is conclusive proof that the risks outweigh the potential benefits, at any point during the study, the researchers must assess whether to continue, modify or immediately stop the study.

Scientific requirements and research protocols

11. Medical research involving human subjects must conform to generally accepted scientific principles, be based on a thorough knowledge of the scientific literature, other relevant sources of information, and adequate laboratory and, as appropriate, animal experimentation. The welfare of animals used for research must be respected.
12. The design and performance of each research study involving human subjects must be clearly described and justified in a research protocol. The protocol should contain a statement of the ethical considerations involved and should indicate how the principles in this Declaration have been addressed. The protocol should include information regarding funding, sponsors, institutional affiliations, potential conflicts of interest, incentives for subjects and information regarding provisions for treating and/or compensating subjects who are harmed as a consequence of participation in the research study.

Research ethics committees

13. The research protocols must be submitted to the concerned research ethics committee for modifications and approval. The committee must be transparent in its functioning and review the research protocol by taking into consideration the laws and regulations of the country or countries in which the research is performed and all the relevant international ethical norms and standards.
14. The committee must have the right to monitor ongoing studies. The researcher must provide monitoring information to the committee, especially information about any serious adverse events. No amendment to the protocol may be made without consideration and approval by the committee. After the end of the study, the researchers must submit a final report to the committee containing a summary of the study's findings and conclusions.

Privacy and confidentiality

15. Every precaution must be taken to protect the privacy of research subjects and the confidentiality of their personal information.

Informed consent

16. Participation by individuals capable of giving informed consent as subjects in medical research must be voluntary. Although it may be appropriate to consult family members or community leaders, no individual capable of giving informed consent may be enrolled in a research study unless he or she freely agrees.
17. In medical research involving human subjects capable of giving informed consent, each potential subject must be adequately informed of the aims, methods, sources of funding, any possible conflicts of interest, institutional affiliations of the researcher, the anticipated benefits and potential risks of the study and the discomfort it may entail, post-study provisions and any other relevant aspects of the study. The potential subject must be informed of the right to refuse to participate in the study or to withdraw consent to participate at any time without reprisal. Special attention should be given to the specific information needs of individual potential subjects as well as to the methods used to deliver the information.
18. After ensuring that the potential subject has understood the information, the physician or another appropriately qualified individual must then seek the potential subject's freely-given informed consent, preferably in writing. If the consent cannot be expressed in writing, the non-written consent must be formally documented and witnessed.
19. All medical research subjects should be given the option of being informed about the general outcome and results of the study.
20. For a potential research subject who is incapable of giving informed consent, the physician must seek informed consent from the legally authorised representative. These individuals must not be included in a research study that has no likelihood of benefit for them unless it is intended to promote the health of the group represented by the potential subject, the research cannot instead be performed with persons capable of providing informed consent, and the research entails only minimal risk and minimal burden.
21. When a potential research subject who is deemed incapable of giving informed consent is able to give assent to decisions about participation in research, the physician must seek that assent in addition to the consent of the legally authorised representative. The potential subject's dissent should be respected.
22. The physician must fully inform the patient which aspects of their care are related to the research. The refusal of a patient to participate in a study or the patient's decision to withdraw from the study must never adversely affect the patient-physician relationship.

Post-trial provisions

23. In advance of a clinical trial, sponsors, researchers and host country governments should make provisions for post-trial access for all participants who still need an intervention identified as beneficial in the trial. This information must also be disclosed to participants during the informed consent process.

Research registration and publication and dissemination of results

24. Every research study involving human subjects must be registered in a publicly accessible database before recruitment of the first subject.
25. Researchers, authors, sponsors, editors and publishers all have ethical obligations with regard to the publication and dissemination of the results of research. Researchers have a duty to make publicly available the results of their research on human subjects and are accountable for the completeness and accuracy of their reports. All parties should adhere to accepted guidelines for ethical reporting. Negative and inconclusive as well as positive results must be published or otherwise made publicly available. Sources of funding, institutional affiliations and conflicts of interest must be declared in the publication. Reports of research not in accordance with the principles of this Declaration should not be accepted for publication.

Unproven interventions in clinical practice

26. In the treatment of an individual patient, where proven interventions do not exist or other known interventions have been ineffective, the physician, after seeking expert advice, with informed consent from the patient or a legally authorised representative, may use an unproven intervention if in the physician's judgement it offers hope of saving life, re-establishing health or alleviating suffering. This intervention should subsequently be made the object of research, designed to evaluate its safety and efficacy. In all cases, new information must be recorded and, where appropriate, made publicly available.

The numbering above is used for reference purposes within this document and does not necessarily reflect the numbering of principles in the Declaration of Helsinki.

2.1.2 CIOMS guidelines for Biomedical Research

The Council of International Organizations of Medical Sciences (CIOMS) has produced a series of international ethical guidelines for biomedical research involving human subjects with the collaboration of the World Health Organization (WHO). The key points of the third in the series (Council for International Organizations of Medical Sciences, 2002) that are also related to the VITALISE project are provided below:

General ethical principles

Three general ethical principles are defined: i) respect for persons' autonomy and protection of persons with impaired autonomy (Respect for persons); ii) maximisation of benefit and minimisation of harm (Beneficence); iii) treat each person in accordance with what is morally right and proper (Justice).

Guidelines

1. The research involving human beings must be ethically justified and scientifically validated.
2. Proposals to conduct research involving human beings must be submitted for review by one or more scientific and ethical review committees
3. The external sponsor and the individual researchers must submit the research protocol for review by a local or national ethics committee in the country of the sponsor.
4. The researcher must obtain informed consent of the prospective participant in the study or her/his authorised representative. Waiver of informed consent is regarded uncommon and it must be approved by an ethical committee.
5. The researcher must provide the prospective participants with detailed information about the study and her/his rights.
6. Researchers and sponsors have a duty to: refrain from unjustified deception, influence or intimidation; seek consent after ascertaining that the individual has assimilated the information; obtain a signed form as evidence of informed consent or justify the lack of, which must be further approved by the concerned ethics committee; renew the consent form if changes are made to the study or at predetermined intervals of a long-term study even if there are no changes.

7. Subjects participating in a research study may be reimbursed, be paid or receive medical services for free. The latter must be approved by the ethical committee.
8. For all biomedical research involving human subjects, the researcher must ensure that potential benefits and risks are reasonably balanced, and risks are minimised
9. Guideline 9 refers to research involving individuals incapable of providing informed consent and it is irrelevant to the VITALISE project.
10. Guideline 10 refers to research involving populations with limited resources, and it is irrelevant to the VITALISE project.
11. Subjects in the controls group of a research study must receive an established effective intervention as a general rule. Ethical acceptable exceptions may apply.
12. Groups or communities to be invited to be subjects of research should be selected in such a way that the burdens and benefits of the research will be equitably distributed. The exclusion of groups or communities that might benefit from study participation must be justified.
13. Special justification is required for inviting vulnerable individuals to serve as research subjects and, if they are selected, the means of protecting their rights and welfare must be strictly applied.
14. Guideline 14 refers to research involving children and it is irrelevant to the VITALISE project.
15. Guideline 9 refers to research involving individuals incapable of providing informed consent and it is irrelevant to the VITALISE project.
16. Ethics committees, researchers or sponsors must not exclude women of reproductive age from biomedical research. The potential risks on her pregnancy and her foetus, must be discussed with the woman, in case she becomes pregnant during the research study.
17. Researchers and ethical review committees should ensure that prospective subjects who are pregnant are adequately informed about the risks and benefits to themselves, their pregnancies, the foetus and their subsequent offspring, as well as to their fertility.
18. The researcher must establish secure safeguards of the confidentiality of subjects' research data. Subjects should be told the limits, legal or other, to the investigators' ability to safeguard confidentiality and the possible consequences of breaches of confidentiality.
19. Researchers should ensure that research subjects who suffer injury as a result of their participation are entitled to free medical treatment for such injury and to such financial or other assistance as would equitably compensate them for any resultant impairment, disability or handicap. In the case of death as a result of their participation, their dependants are entitled to compensation. Subjects must not be asked to waive the right to compensation.
20. In externally sponsored collaborative research, sponsors and researchers are ethically obliged to strengthen the capacity for ethical and scientific review and biomedical research in host countries that lack such capacity.
21. External sponsors are ethically obligated to provide health-care services that are essential for the safe conduct of the study, as treatment for subjects that suffered injuries during the study, or as part of the commitment of the sponsor to make a beneficial product from the study, reasonably available to the population or community concerned.

For the detailed guidelines the reader is referred to the full publication of the International Guidelines on Biomedical Research Involving Human Subjects (Council for International Organizations of Medical Sciences, 2002) that is also available online .

2.1.3 Universal Declaration on Bioethics and Human Research

The Universal Declaration on Bioethics and Human Rights (UNESCO, 2005) constitutes a compilation of ethical guidelines regarding medicine, life sciences and technologies as applied to human beings. It was produced by the United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) in the context of its Bioethics Program. The articles of the declaration relevant to VITALISE are summarised below:

3 – Human dignity and human rights

1. Human dignity, human rights and fundamental freedoms are to be fully respected.

2. The interests and welfare of the individual should have priority over the sole interest of science or society.

4 – Benefit and harm

In applying and advancing scientific knowledge, medical practice and associated technologies, direct and indirect benefits to patients, research participants and other affected individuals should be maximized and any possible harm to such individuals should be minimized.

5 – Autonomy and individual responsibility

The autonomy of persons to make decisions, while taking responsibility for those decisions and respecting the autonomy of others, is to be respected. For persons who are not capable of exercising autonomy, special measures are to be taken to protect their rights and interests.

6 – Consent

1. Any preventive, diagnostic and therapeutic medical intervention is only to be carried out with the prior, free and informed consent of the person concerned, based on adequate information. The consent should, where appropriate, be express and may be withdrawn by the person concerned at any time and for any reason without disadvantage or prejudice.

2. Scientific research should only be carried out with the prior, free, express and informed consent of the person concerned. The information should be adequate, provided in a comprehensible form and should include modalities for withdrawal of consent. Consent may be withdrawn by the person concerned at any time and for any reason without any disadvantage or prejudice. Exceptions to this principle should be made only in accordance with ethical and legal standards adopted by States, consistent with the principles and provisions set out in this Declaration, in particular in Article 27, and international human rights law.

8 – Respect for human vulnerability and personal integrity

In applying and advancing scientific knowledge, medical practice and associated technologies, human vulnerability should be taken into account. Individuals and groups of special vulnerability should be protected and the personal integrity of such individuals respected.

9 – Privacy and confidentiality

The privacy of the persons concerned and the confidentiality of their personal information should be respected. To the greatest extent possible, such information should not be used or disclosed for purposes other than those for which it was collected or consented to, consistent with international law, in particular international human rights law.

10 – Equality, justice and equity

The fundamental equality of all human beings in dignity and rights is to be respected so that they are treated justly and equitably.

11 – Non-discrimination and non-stigmatization

No individual or group should be discriminated against or stigmatized on any grounds, in violation of human dignity, human rights and fundamental freedoms.

12 – Respect for cultural diversity and pluralism

The importance of cultural diversity and pluralism should be given due regard. However, such considerations are not to be invoked to infringe upon human dignity, human rights and fundamental freedoms, nor upon the principles set out in this Declaration, nor to limit their scope.

13 – Solidarity and cooperation

Solidarity among human beings and international cooperation towards that end are to be encouraged.

14 – Social responsibility and health

1. The promotion of health and social development for their people is a central purpose of governments that all sectors of society share.
2. Taking into account that the enjoyment of the highest attainable standard of health is one of the fundamental rights of every human being without distinction of race, religion, political belief, economic or social condition, progress in science and technology should advance:
 - (a) access to quality health care and essential medicines, especially for the health of women and children, because health is essential to life itself and must be considered to be a social and human good;
 - (b) access to adequate nutrition and water;
 - (c) improvement of living conditions and the environment;
 - (d) elimination of the marginalization and the exclusion of persons on the basis of any grounds;
 - (e) reduction of poverty and illiteracy.

15 – Sharing of benefits

1. Benefits resulting from any scientific research and its applications should be shared with society as a whole and within the international community, in particular with developing countries. In giving effect to this principle, benefits may take any of the following forms:
 - (a) special and sustainable assistance to, and acknowledgement of, the persons and groups that have taken part in the research;
 - (b) access to quality health care;
 - (c) provision of new diagnostic and therapeutic modalities or products stemming from research;
 - (d) support for health services;
 - (e) access to scientific and technological knowledge;
 - (f) capacity-building facilities for research purposes;
 - (g) other forms of benefit consistent with the principles set out in this Declaration.
2. Benefits should not constitute improper inducements to participate in research.

6 – Protecting future generations

The impact of life sciences on future generations, including on their genetic constitution, should be given due regard.

Application of the principles

18 – Decision-making and addressing bioethical issues

1. Professionalism, honesty, integrity and transparency in decision-making should be promoted, in particular declarations of all conflicts of interest and appropriate sharing of knowledge. Every endeavour should be made to use the best available scientific knowledge and methodology in addressing and periodically reviewing bioethical issues.
2. Persons and professionals concerned and society as a whole should be engaged in dialogue on a regular basis.
3. Opportunities for informed pluralistic public debate, seeking the expression of all relevant opinions, should be promoted.

19 – Ethics committees

Independent, multidisciplinary and pluralist ethics committees should be established, promoted and supported at the appropriate level in order to:

- (a) assess the relevant ethical, legal, scientific and social issues related to research projects involving human beings;
- (b) provide advice on ethical problems in clinical settings;
- (c) assess scientific and technological developments, formulate recommendations and contribute to the preparation of guidelines on issues within the scope of this Declaration;
- (d) foster debate, education and public awareness of, and engagement in, bioethics.

20 – Risk assessment and management

Appropriate assessment and adequate management of risk related to medicine, life sciences and associated technologies should be promoted.

21 – Transnational practices

1. States, public and private institutions, and professionals associated with transnational activities should endeavour to ensure that any activity within the scope of this Declaration, undertaken, funded or otherwise pursued in whole or in part in different States, is consistent with the principles set out in this Declaration.
2. When research is undertaken or otherwise pursued in one or more States (the host State(s)) and funded by a source in another State, such research should be the object of an appropriate level of ethical review in the host State(s) and the State in which the funder is located. This review should be based on ethical and legal standards that are consistent with the principles set out in this Declaration.
3. Transnational health research should be responsive to the needs of host countries, and the importance of research contributing to the alleviation of urgent global health problems should be recognized.
4. When negotiating a research agreement, terms for collaboration and agreement on the benefits of research should be established with equal participation by those party to the negotiation.
5. States should take appropriate measures, both at the national and international levels, to combat bioterrorism and illicit traffic in organs, tissues, samples, genetic resources and genetic-related materials.

Final provisions

Article 26 – Interrelation and complementarity of the principles

This Declaration is to be understood as a whole and the principles are to be understood as complementary and interrelated. Each principle is to be considered in the context of the other principles, as appropriate and relevant in the circumstances.

The relevant to VITALISE guidelines presented in the previous sections represent the most prominent reference documents regarding ethical guidelines that are acceptable worldwide. In the following sections, Europe-specific and national regulations are presented.

2.2 European regulations and Directives

2.2.1 Research Ethics

There are mainly three texts that govern ethics at EU level:

The Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union (European Union, 2012) which recognizes a range of personal, civil, political, economic and social rights. The Lisbon Treaty incorporates the Charter into the Treaty on the European Union, giving the charter an equal legal effect, and states that all European legislation needs to conform to the principles of the Charter. Consequently, this also applies to the European research policy. Key articles of the Charter are:

Article 3 – Right to the integrity of the person;

Article 7 – Respect for private and family life;

Article 8 – Protection of Personal Data;

Article 13 – Freedom of the Arts and Sciences.

The European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR) (Council of Europe, 1950), which is an international legally binding treaty to protect human rights and fundamental freedoms in Europe.

The European Code of Conduct for Research integrity (ALLEA 2017) (ALLEA - All European Academies, 2017), which sets out good research practice to guide researchers in their work.

The Regulation (EU) 536/2014 on clinical trials on medicinal products for human use, and repealing Directive 2001/20/EC aimed to harmonize the administrative provisions governing clinical trials in the Union.

2.2.2 Ethics and Data protection in EU

Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data and repealing Directive 95/46/EC8 (General Data Protection Regulation).

The key points of GDPR are:

Introduction of a set of rights for all EU citizens:

- Right to be informed
- Right of access
- Right to rectification
- Right to erasure
- Right to restrict of processing
- Right to data portability
- Right to object
- Right regarding automated decision making
- Right to be notified in case of data breach

Processing of personal data under GDPR requires explicit consent instead of implicit.

Distinction between Controller and Processor of personal data

Data protection by design and by default

Data minimization principle

Introduction of Data Protection Impact Assessment

Data protection authorities will be able to fine companies who do not comply with EU rules up to 4% of their global annual turnover.

VITALISE will also comply with the Art. 29 Guidelines on Article 49 of Regulation 2016/679, adopted on 6th of February 2018, the Art. 29 Guidelines on transparency under Regulation 2016/679, revised and adopted on 11th of April 2018 and Art 29. guidelines on consent under Regulation 2016/679, revised and adopted on 10th of April 2018.

2.3 National Regulations

This section provides an overview of the ethical regulatory framework in each country, where partners of the VITALISE project reside and where a significant amount of data will be collected for the scopes of the project. It must be noted *a priori* that national legislation in all cases is harmonised with international guidelines and key EU regulations.

2.3.1 Austria

The relevant national legislation concerning the VITALISE project as carried out in Austria are the following:

Data Protection guidelines for consideration in ethical applications

- Bundesgesetz über den Schutz personenbezogener Daten (Datenschutzgesetz – DSGVO) as amended by: Federal Law Gazette I No. 14/2019 (Federal Act concerning the Protection of Personal Data)

Ethical guidelines for Health-related Research involving Human Participants

- Arzneimittelgesetz – AMG 6 May 2019 (Medicinal Products Act)

- Bundesgesetz über die Organisation der Universitäten und ihre Studien (Universitätsgesetz 2002 – UG) as amended by: Federal Law Gazette I No. 3/2019 (Universities Act).

2.3.2 Belgium

The relevant national legislation concerning the VITALISE project as carried out in Belgium are the following:

Data Protection guidelines for consideration in ethical applications

- Act of 3 December 2017
- Act of 30 July 2018 - Act on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data

Ethical guidelines for Health-related Research involving Human Participants

- Law of 7 May 2004 concerning experiments on the human person.
- Royal Decree of 30 June 2004 establishing measures for the implementation of the law of 7 May 2004 concerning experiments on the human person with regard to clinical trials on medicinal products for human use
- Royal Decree of 18 May 2006 amending the Royal Decree of 30 June 2004 establishing measures for the implementation of the law of 7 May 2004 concerning experiments on the human person with regard to clinical trials on medicinal products for human use
- Royal Decree of 04 April 2014 establishing measures for the implementation of the law of 7 May 2004 concerning experiments on the human person, with regard to the ethical committee
- Act of 7 May 2017 - on clinical trials on medicinal products for human use

2.3.3 Bulgaria

The relevant national legislation concerning the VITALISE project as carried out in Bulgaria are the following:

Data Protection guidelines for consideration in ethical applications

- Bulgarian Personal Data Protection Act (PDPA) as amended on 26 of November 2019

Ethical guidelines for Health-related Research involving Human Participants

- Ethics Committee for Multi-Centre Trials (Drug Law, Article 103)
- Central Ethics Committee (Drug Law, Article 107)
- Ethics committees established in the treatment establishments (e.g. regional hospitals) (Drug Law, Article 103) and in other institutions (e.g. universities, scientific organizations) where biomedical research is conducted (Health Act, Article 203)

2.3.4 Canada

In Canada, research involving human subjects must adhere to the principles and articles stipulated in the latest version of the Tri-Council Policy Statement Ethical Conduct For Research Involving Humans (TCPS). The three core principles are respect for persons, concern for welfare, and justice. Researchers are responsible for knowing about and adhering to the standards articulated therein. The TCPS guides the review of all research conducted at institutions funded by any of those 3 agencies (i.e., all Canadian universities and many hospitals) and is considered the minimal standard for the ethical review of research involving humans. The interpretation and enforcement of the principles found within the TCPS is left to universities and hospitals, most of which have “Research Ethics Boards” (REBs) whose job it is to review research proposals and monitor ongoing research to ensure compliance with the TCPS. In addition, Canada is recognized as providing adequate protection pursuant to GDPR, meaning that data transfers to Canada will be assimilated to intra-EU transmissions of data.

2.3.5 Finland

The relevant national legislation concerning the VITALISE project as carried out in Finland are the following:

Data Protection guidelines for consideration in ethical applications

- Act of 3 December 2017
- Act of 30 July 2018 - Act on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data

Ethical guidelines for Health-related Research involving Human Participants

- Law of 7 May 2004 concerning experiments on the human person
- Royal Decree of 30 June 2004 establishing measures for the implementation of the law of 7 May 2004 concerning experiments on the human person with regard to clinical trials on medicinal products for human use
- Royal Decree of 18 May 2006 amending the Royal Decree of 30 June 2004 establishing measures for the implementation of the law of 7 May 2004 concerning experiments on the human person with regard to clinical trials on medicinal products for human use
- Royal Decree of 04 April 2014 establishing measures for the implementation of the law of 7 May 2004 concerning experiments on the human person, with regard to the ethical committee
- Act of 7 May 2017 - on clinical trials on medicinal products for human use

2.3.6 France

The relevant national legislation concerning the VITALISE project as carried out in France are the following:

Data Protection guidelines for consideration in ethical applications

- "Loi informatique et libertés", 1978 (Act n°78-17 of 6 January 1978 on Data Processing, Data Files and Individual Liberties amended by the Act of 6 August 2004, relating to the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data)
- Law No. 2018-493 of June 20, 2018
- Order No. 2018-1125 of December 12, 2018, adopted pursuant to Article 32 of Law No. 2018-493
- Decree No. 2019-536

Ethical guidelines for Health-related Research involving Human Participants

- the French Comités de protection des personnes (CPP – Individual Protection Committees). CPPs represent the French equivalent to the Ethical Research.

2.3.7 Greece

The relevant national legislation concerning the VITALISE project as carried out in Greece are the following:

Data Protection guidelines for consideration in ethical applications

- Law 2472/1997;
- Law 3471/2006 (Protection of personal data and privacy in the electronic telecommunications sector and amendment of law 2472/1997).
- Law 4624/2019

Ethical guidelines for Health-related Research involving Human Participants

- Ministerial order ΔΥΓ3/89292

2.3.8 Hungary

The relevant national legislation concerning the VITALISE project as carried out in Hungary are the following:

Data Protection guidelines for consideration in ethical applications

- Act CXII of 2011
- Act XXXVIII of 2018 (amendment of Act CXII of 2011)

Ethical guidelines for Health-related Research involving Human Participants

- Decree Nr. 23/2002 of the Minister of Health
- Health Act, § 159

2.3.9 Italy

The relevant national legislation concerning the VITALISE project as carried out in Italy are the following:

Data Protection guidelines for consideration in ethical applications

- Legislative Decree n.196 of 30 June 2003 as amended by Legislative Decree n.101 of 10 August 2018.

Ethical guidelines for Health-related Research involving Human Participants

- In statistic or scientific research (human related), special ethics rules apply for data protection: art.20, clause 4 of the Italian Legislative Decree n.101 of 19 December 2018.

2.3.10 Netherlands

The relevant national legislation concerning the VITALISE project as carried out in the Netherlands are the following:

Data Protection guidelines for consideration in ethical applications

- GDPR Implementation Act (UAVG) 22 May 2018

Ethical guidelines for Health-related Research involving Human Participants

- Medical Research Human Subjects Act 26 February 1998
- Medical Research(Human Subjects) Compulsory Insurance Decree 23 June 2003
- Central Review of Medical Research Involving Human Subjects Decree as amended in 3 January 2006
- Regulations for medical research with people 9 July 2015
- Conclude scientific research with medicines 16 December 2005

2.3.11 Spain

The relevant national legislation concerning the VITALISE project as carried out in Spain are the following:

Data Protection guidelines for consideration in ethical applications

- Organic Law on Personal Data Protection 15/1999
- Spanish Agency for Data Protection, 2016
- Ley Orgánica 3/2018, de 5 de diciembre, de Protección de Datos Personales y garantía de los derechos digitales

Ethical guidelines for Health-related Research involving Human Participants

- CIOMS International Ethical Guidelines for Health-related Research Involving Humans
- Declaration of Helsinki – Ethical Principles for Medical Research Involving Human Subjects

- Ley 14/2007, de 3 julio, de Investigación Biomédica
- Ley 14/1986, de 25 de abril, General de Sanidad - General Health Law
- Ley 41/2002, de 14 de noviembre, básica reguladora de la autonomía del paciente y de derechos y obligaciones en materia de información y documentación clínica - Basic law regulating patient autonomy and rights and obligations in terms of information and clinical documentation
- Ley 33/2011, de 4 de octubre - General Law of Public Health
- Real Decreto 1090/2015, de 4 de diciembre, por el que se regulan los ensayos clínicos con medicamentos, los Comités de Ética de la Investigación con medicamentos y el Registro Español de Estudios Clínicos – regulation of clinical trials with medicines, the Research Ethics Committees and the Spanish Registry of Clinical Studies

2.4 The case of electronic informed consent

As of 01/07/2016, when Regulation (EU) No 910/2014⁶⁷ took effect, the EU recognizes e-identification means and electronic trust services, such as e-signatures, e-seals, e-registered delivery services, time stamping, and website authentication. For the purposes of VITALISE, tools for acquiring informed consent through electronic means will be utilized. Specifically, the electronic informed consent (eIC) and the electronic consent form (eCF) will be used, as they are appropriate for research studies that engage with their participants remotely and help to significantly accelerate the informed consent procedure.

The guidelines concerning the use of eIC in clinical research studies, as issued by the eConsent Task Force team under the auspices of the European Clinical Research Organization (CRO) Federation (EUCROF), are summarized in the following points:

All elements of the informed consent contained on the eCF must be in a language comprehensible and unambiguous to the concerned individual.

The informed consent given freely by the subject can be revokable

The remote signing of the eIC should be accompanied by the electronic documentation of all the interactive responses of the concerned individual.

All subjects must be given the opportunity to freely and firmly make inquiries and ask for clarification from the investigators through electronic means, such as live chat, video conferences, online or offline messaging etc.

The information and materials used by the researchers to inform the concerned subject must be specific

The information and materials used by the researchers to inform the concerned subject may be of a multimodal nature (using electronic media), i.e., it may contain graphics and/or audiovisual aids, as long as the information, regardless of form, remains complete and understandable.

A copy of the signed eIC should be provided to each subject, along with easy access to all relevant information and materials encapsulated in the eCF.

The computerized system used for the storage and preservation of the eIC must be secured with the application of access restrictions, i.e. only specified researchers may access the eCF database.

Any amendments made to the eIC must be thoroughly review and approved by a research ethics committee (REC).

3 Devices safety regulations

This section presents the international (WHO) perspective and the European regulatory framework regarding medical devices safety, as well as the common standards and certifications on which the design and development of electronic medical devices must conform to.

3.1 Medical Devices Regulations

This section presents the international (WHO) and the European regulatory framework regarding medical devices safety, as well as the common standards on which medical devices must conform to.

3.1.1 WHO perspective

According to the Global Harmonization Task Force (GHTF) - now replaced by the International Medical Device Regulators Forum - (GHTF document SG1/N029R11) and highlighted also by WHO (WHO, 2003), a harmonised definition of medical device is the following (p. vii):

"Medical device means any instrument, apparatus, implement, machine, appliance, implant, in vitro reagent or calibrator, software, material or other similar or related article, intended by the manufacturer to be used, alone or in combination, for human beings for one or more of the specific purposes of:

- *diagnosis, prevention, monitoring, treatment or alleviation of disease*
- *diagnosis, monitoring, treatment, alleviation of or compensation for an injury*
- *investigation, replacement, modification, or support of the anatomy or of a physiological process*
- *supporting or sustaining life*
- *control of conception*
- *disinfection of medical devices*

providing information for medical purposes by means of in vitro examination of specimens derived from the human body and which does not achieve its primary intended action in or on the human body by pharmacological, immunological or metabolic means, but which may be assisted in its function by such means."

According to WHO and as reported in its Medical Device Regulations document (WHO, 2003) (Cheng, 2003), also available online, the optimal assurance of medical devices safety has several essential elements:

1. *Absolute safety cannot be guaranteed:* Safety can be considered only in relative terms as medical device problems cannot be detected until extensive market experience is gained.
2. *It is a risk management issue:* Device safety can be translated into a risk assessment of the potential for the use of a medical device to result in safety problems and harm. Risk assessment of medical devices is based on the experience of health care professionals and on safety design engineering.
3. *It is closely aligned with device effectiveness/performance:* A medical device is clinically effective when it produces the effect intended by the manufacturer relative to the medical condition. Device performance is more general, it may include additional functions, not related to clinical effectiveness, and it is easier to measure objectively. Performance and safety of medical devices are often considered together.
4. *It must be considered throughout the life span of the device:* The major phases in the life span of a medical device are: 1) Conception and development; 2) Manufacture; 3) Packaging and labelling; 4) Advertising; 5) Sale; 6) Use; 7) Disposal. During VITALISE and regarding the new sensors developed within the project, Phase 1 is of particular interest. Phase 2-7 are part of the exploitation strategy that the project will adopt. In the case of Phase 1, soundness of concept and adequacy of design, construction, and testing require the scrutiny of experts to ensure that design and performance do not impose unwarranted risks.
5. *It requires shared responsibility among stakeholders:* The main stakeholders involved throughout the life span of a device are: a) the manufacturer (phases 1-3), b) the vendor (phases 4-5), and c) the user (phases 6-7). All three play critical roles in ensuring the safety of medical devices. The most important factor that ensures the cooperation of all these stakeholders is an informed and common understanding of the issues. Shared understanding and responsibility are achieved through communication and mutual education, which can be effectively achieved by having all stakeholders participate in establishing the process that ensures safety and performance of medical devices.

The WHO Medical Devices Regulations document (WHO, 2003) also presents, amongst other international and national regulations, the respective European regulations (Chapter 3) and offers an introduction to device standards (Chapter 5), two subject areas that are also analysed in Section 4.1.2 and Section 4.5.2, respectively, of the present report.

3.1.2 EU Regulatory Framework

The medical devices and their corresponding software need to be fully compliant as of 26th of May 2021 with REGULATION (EU) 2017/745 on medical devices (MDR) amending Directive 2001/83/EC, Regulation (EC) No 178/2002 and Regulation (EC) No 1223/2009 and repealing Council Directives 90/385/EEC and 93/42/EEC previously in force. The MDR applies to all existing devices in addition to new devices. Also, in general, a medical device cannot be marketed in Europe without carrying a CE marking. A CE marking is applied by the manufacturer and means that the device meets the relevant regulatory requirements and, when used as intended, works properly and is acceptably safe.

Regarding, MDR reads in Annex I that *“Devices shall achieve the performance intended by their manufacturer and shall be designed and manufactured in such a way that, during normal conditions of use, they are suitable for their intended purpose. They shall be safe and effective and shall not compromise the clinical condition or the safety of patients, or the safety and health of users or, where applicable, other persons, provided that any risks which may be associated with their use constitute acceptable risks when weighed against the benefits to the patient and are compatible with a high level of protection of health and safety, taking into account the generally acknowledged state of the art.”* In Annex I, General Safety and Performance Requirements (GSPR), which included chapters on general requirements, design and manufacture, and information supplied with the device. Manufacturers will need to demonstrate how they have met each requirement of the annex.

Regarding standards in the EU, harmonised standard are issued after the request of the EC to a recognised European Standards Organisation: Comité Européen de Normalisation (CEN), the European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization (CENELEC), or the European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI). They are used to demonstrate compliance with relevant EU legislation of products, services, or processes. The references of harmonised standards must be published in the Official Journal of the European Union. Adherence to these standards, allows manufacturers and service providers to claim "presumption of conformity" allowing them to put their products and services on the EU common market.

3.2 Standards and Certifications for electronic devices

3.2.1 Standards

Medical devices are conceived, developed and fabricated according to the requirements of harmonized norm EN 60601-1-2:2021 (*IEC 60601-1:2021 SER, 2021*), which pertains to the general safety, electromagnetic compatibility and testing. Companies are requested to have a quality management system in place, which includes not only the base ISO 9001:2015 quality management system, but also the ISO 13485:2016, which is a specific extension applicable to medical device manufacturers.

In addition, MDR 745/2017 establishes the criteria in order for a device to be considered medical and the guidelines for classification of medical devices in the light of four established categories (Class I, Class IIa, Class IIb and Class III) and requirements that devices need to comply with. As a part of the classification process, a risk analysis with foreseen mitigation measures is required also; this is regulated by the harmonized norm ISO 14971:2019.

According to the mode of communication and power managements every device implements other regulations may also be appropriate for application. Specifically, the IEC 60601-1-2:2021 (*IEC 60601-1:2021 SER, 2021*), regarding the manner in which a device is powered (internally, via a

battery, or externally); the IEC 61000-3-3:2013 (*IEC 61000-3-3:2013+AMD1:2017+AMD2:2021 CSV, 2021*), related to device electromagnetic compatibility (e.g. voltage fluctuations, flicker emissions, etc.); the IEC 61000-3-2:2018 (*IEC 61000-3-2:2018+AMD1:2020 CSV, 2020*), concerning harmonic emissions; the CISPR 11:2015 (*CISPR 11:2015+AMD1:2016+AMD2:2019 CSV, 2019*), for devices communicating via radio channels, regarding radiofrequency power and emissions levels.

4 Data management regulations

4.1 Data protection regulations

As already identified in Section 2 and in particular in sections 2.2.2 and 2.3, the corresponding transpositions of GDPR in national laws have been outlined. European Commission has reformed and harmonized the data protection rules in the EU with the GDPR entered into force in May 2016, and applied from 25 May 2018. The objective of this new set of rules is to give citizens back control over of their personal data, and to simplify the regulatory environment for business.

Under EU law, personal data can only be processed legally under strict conditions. Furthermore, whoever processes personal data must protect it from misuse and must respect certain rights of the data owners which are guaranteed by EU law. In an event of a data breach, the local data protection authority must be notified.

The main points of GDPR regarding data management are the following:

Data controllers and processors are responsible for data protection

The regulation applies not only domestic EU organizations but everyone that may have data of EU citizens or residents.

Rules on transferring data on EU citizens outside the EU. Transfer of personal data outside the Extended European Area (EEA) is allowed under a. decisions of adequacy of local law, b. EC standard contractual clauses

The regulation introduces certain rights to the personal data subjects (see section 2.2.2)

Controllers are responsible to inform users about their rights

Introduction of opt-in rule. Data subjects must opt-in for their data to be processed

Controllers and processors must follow the principles of security and privacy by default and by design

Encryption and pseudonymization: Controllers and processors must implement appropriate technical and organizational measures, such as encryption or pseudonymization.

4.2 Data exchange and access rights regulations

Access and exchange of research data must comply with the standard ethical guidelines on data privacy and GDPR reported in Section 2.2.2 and Section 4.1. In addition, certain definitions and obligations are included in the Grant Agreement (GA) (*Grant Agreement Number 101007990 - VITALISE, 2021*) of Horizon 2020. The latter are included in Articles 26, 27, 29, 31, 36, and 37 of the GA. In addition, to the provisions regarding data ownership and intra-consortium exchanges of the GA, under GDPR, any transfer of personal data or special categories of personal data will be performed after the signing of a controller-processor agreement or a joint-controller agreement between the sender and the recipient.

4.3 Good practices on the use of data in dissemination activities

Sharing of individual related data in the context of scientific research, including dissemination activities, is an increasingly important topic since patient privacy as well as retention of data must be ensured. The International Committee of Medical Journal Editors' Uniform Requirements for

Manuscripts Submitted to Biomedical Journals require that patient privacy be protected, and maintaining confidentiality and privacy is harmonized across the EEA under GDPR.

With regard to dissemination activities the standard practice is the usage of aggregated data which protects the privacy of the participants. When dissemination activities include the submission of research data to open-research repositories, it must be fully anonymized. Despite journal and funder policies requiring data sharing, universally agreed definitions as to what constitutes anonymized data are required

The HIPAA (United States, 2004) identifies of 18 items that need to be removed from patient information to be considered anonymous for the purposes of sharing medical information, but it was not designed with publication in academic journals in mind.

Indicative guidance includes the following:

- Consent for publication of appropriately anonymized raw data in open research repositories must be provided from the participants in clinical research.
- Direct identifiers such as patients' names should be removed from datasets; datasets that contain should be reviewed by an independent researcher or REC before submission to open repositories.
- Data anonymization: Data controllers are responsible for anonymizing datasets
- Controlled access to data, including use of a Joint controller/Data sharing agreement: A legally binding Joint-controller/Data sharing agreement should be in place

4.4 VITALISE compliance

This section details an initial overview of the processes and strategies that will be applied, in the lifecycle of the VITALISE project, so that data acquisition is completed in compliance with all corresponding ethical regulations and guidelines. Furthermore, it provides an evaluation of the general level of concern (low, medium, high) concerning aspects of data collection.

4.4.1 JRAs

The Horizon 2020 Project 'Virtual Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Infrastructure' (VITALISE), funded by the European Union (under grant agreement no. 101007990; April 2021- March 2024), unites 19 partners (AIT, AUTH, AV, CERTH, ENoLL, GAIA, INTRAS, LAUREA, LICALAB, LLSA, McGill, SIT, TREBAG, TUE, UDEM, UPM, VICOM, VILABS, WITA) across 11 countries. VITALISE aims to harmonize Living Lab procedures and open Living Lab Infrastructures as a means to facilitate and promote research activities in the Health and Wellbeing domain in Europe and beyond. To do so, the VITALISE consortium will conduct joint research activities (JRAs) in the fields of rehabilitation, transitional care and everyday living environments, that combine and capitalize on research experience and expertise from the different Living Labs in the consortium and create innovation testbeds for the harmonized procedures and infrastructures.

JRA1 – Rehabilitation supported by technology

JRA1 is in the field of rehabilitation through the use of innovative technology. This study's main goal is to investigate the potential of innovative technologies for rehabilitation through living lab methodologies. This JRA has the following aims: (1) to assess how different stakeholders across multiple countries view the role of technology in rehabilitation; (2) to collect suggestions regarding specific rehabilitation innovations; (3) to perform small-scale pilot studies providing insights into end user experiences and usability of six selected cognitive and/or motor rehabilitation interventions; and (4) to explore the effects of these pilot interventions through self-report, physiological, and motor data of small samples.

Partners from Austria (AIT), Belgium (ENoLL, LICALAB), Bulgaria (AV), Canada (McGill, UDEM), Finland (LAUREA), France (LISA), Greece (AUTH, VILABS), Hungary (TREBAG), Italy (WITA), and Spain (GAIA, INTRAS, UPM, VICOM) will be involved in JRA1. From these AUTH, GAIA, INTRAS LAUREA, LICALAB, LISA, McGill, TREBAG, UPM, UDEM, and VILABS are the engaged partners,

with AUTH, GAIA, INTRAS, LICALAB, McGill and UDEM carrying out their investigations in Living Lab environments.

JRA2 – Transitional care

JRA2 is in the field of transitional care. This study's main goal is to investigate if information related to mobility, functionality etc., collected during and right after hospitalization, can help predict re-admissions, adverse events, and/or care pathways in patients with multimorbidities. This JRA has the following aims: (1) to identify the tendencies of healthcare professionals, informal caregivers and patients in using technological tools for supporting the transitional process; (2) to perform small-scale pilot studies providing insights into end user experiences and preferences; (3) to provide information to healthcare professionals/informal caregivers/patients in a comprehensive, useful and easily exploitable way.

Partners from Austria (AIT), Belgium (ENoLL, LICALAB), Bulgaria (AV), Canada (McGill, UDEM), Finland (LAUREA), France (LISA), Greece (AUTH, VILABS), Hungary (TREBAG), Italy (WITA), and Spain (INTRAS, UPM, VICOM) will be involved in JRA2. AUTH, McGill and UDEM will carry out their investigation in clinical and Living Lab environments, LAUREA will carry their investigation in a clinical environment, and INTRAS, LICALAB, and UPM will carry out their investigations in home and Living Lab environments.

JRA3 – Everyday living environments

JRA3 is in the field of everyday living. This study's main goal is the collection of big-data from everyday living activities inside and outside the house in order to create dynamic personas that are natively multidimensional and will be used for care personalization in real-time. This JRA has the following aims: (1) to investigate how "smart" spaces, (cities, towns) can be adapted for the practice of sports (noncompetitive) by elders, contributing to their health; (2) to perform small scale evaluate, refine and adjust Living Lab solutions and facilitate their implementation in home environments; (3) to investigate new state of the art technologies that support active and healthy ageing and methodologies for new use case of smart environments.

Partners from Austria (AIT), Belgium (ENoLL, LICALAB), Bulgaria (AV), Canada (UDEM), Finland (LAUREA), France (LISA), Greece (AUTH, CERTH, VILABS), Hungary (TREBAG), Italy (WITA), and Spain (GAIA, INTRAS, UPM, VICOM) will be involved in JRA3. From these, AIT, AUTH, GAIA, INTRAS LAUREA, LICALAB, McGill, TREBAG, and UDEM are the engaged partners, with AUTH, GAIA, INTRAS, LICALAB, McGill and UDEM carrying out their investigations in Living Lab environments.

4.4.1.1 Research Ethics compliance

All JRAs will use the eConsent process. Participants will be provided with a link, which will redirect them to the detailed consent form on the VITALISE project website, where they can choose to give their consent or not, through the electronic signing of the eIC. Only after the concerned individual has completed the electronic informed consent process may they be considered as a participant/end-user of the VITALISE project.

To this aim, the form the eIC will be presented in, and the manner in which the subjects may interact with it will be based upon the following:

- All information contained in the eIC will be presented as scrollable text with clear sectioning, while utilizing a user-friendly reading format (i.e., white background, appropriately sized black font).
- All information presented will be in a language comprehensible to the concerned individual and scientific and technical terms will be described in an appropriate manner.
- Participants will be able to obtain the form after following the corresponding link provided to them (through electronic means), after being informed of its function (consent) and format (language, presentation etc.).
- After the signing process is complete, participants will be provided with a copy of their signed eCF.

- In case of amendments to the eCF that may affect the participants willingness to participate in the project studies, participants will be notified (via electronic means, in a timely fashion) and provided with a new link to the amended eIC, which they can choose to sign or not.

Concerning the eIC content:

- The information included in the eIC will outline the objectives, methodology, processes, any benefits and possible risk of the project's studies.
- The information included in the eIC will explicitly mention all the data that will be collected, who will process it, where it will be stored and for how long.
- The information included in the eIC will explicitly mention all the participant's rights derived from GDPR and local law.
- It will inform the concerned individual that their participation is voluntary and that they have the option to withdraw at any time without any repercussions or effect on their current treatment.
- A contact person will be available to the participant to withdraw from the study or exercise her rights derived from GDPR
- The information included in the eIC will include an Incidentals Findings Policy and a Data Dissemination policy (If applicable)

Following the previously mentioned guide, it is expected that the informed consent over study participation will be freely-given by all concerned individuals.

Regulatory framework compliance: Ethics approval will be acquired from the authorities of all 11 countries and 19 organizations that participate as partners in the VITALISE project, for all three JRAs before the enrollment of the first participant.

The design of eIC will be completed according to EUCROF guidelines and the EU regulation No 910/2014 (eIDAS Regulation) will be used to evaluate the acceptance of the eIC. (as outlined in section 2.4).

The VITALISE project will comply with all international, European and national regulations (as detailed in Section 2) concerning the research data sourcing process by following the previously mentioned strategy.

Concerns: Complete anonymization of the collected data during the JRAs will not be possible due to the nature of data (voice, video). The e-consent schema will provide the possibility to all participants to exercise their rights derived from GDPR, although some of them might be hindered due to lack of expertise with technology. Alternative methods of communication will be provided to such participants, such as telephone or face-to-face meetings etc. Level of concern: medium

4.4.1.2 Devices Safety compliance

The regulations and standard concerning electronic devices have been outlined in Section 3.2 For the purposed of the VITALISE project, data collection, in all JRAs, will be carried out through the use of off-the-self devices (smartwatches, cameras, microphones, sensors, VR headsets, etc), which are all tested and certified. Additionally, some partners will use a CE marked human centrifuge, as well as, EEG, ECG and EMG all of which are certified medical devices.

Concerns: Considering the above mentioned information, the level of concern for the safety of the devices (off-the-shelf) to be used for the VITALISE data collection, generated from human activity tracking, biosignal monitoring, emotion detection etc., is considered low.

4.5 Open calls for researchers

This section provides an initial report on the procedures that will be followed during the open call for external researchers stages of the VITALISE project to be ethically compliant with the appropriate regulations and guidelines. Additionally, the general level of concern (low, medium, high) arising from data collection aspects is evaluated.

4.5.1 Research Ethics compliance

Visiting researchers will be required to adhere to the ethical standards as described in this deliverable. The procedures to be followed are described in 4.4.1.1. In addition, visiting researchers will be required to sign a Non-Disclosure Agreement with the receiving Living Lab.

Regulatory framework compliance: same as 4.4.1.1

Concerns: same as 4.4.1.1

4.5.2 Devices Safety compliance

The devices used by the visiting researchers will be the same with the ones in JRAs.

Concerns: same as 4.4.1.2

4.6 General management of adverse events

Every attempt will be made to ensure the safety of the participants, there are risks of adverse events in every research activity. In the event of an adverse effect, general procedures should be followed to eliminate or minimize the risk of further harm to the participant.

These procedures include:

The Living Labs should have a health and safety statement that will include an emergency plan for adverse events. Medical staff from the relevant VITALISE partner, will be responsible for performing any required examinations prior to the data collection. Appropriated medical staff will have knowledge of this information, be in touch with participants in the JRA, and may instruct the partial or total cessation of the data collection in case of a foreseeable adverse outcome.

For JRAs that include physical activity, VITALISE medical staff should inform participants prior to their enrolment that in case they experience physical activity related adverse effects (e.g., cramps, tachycardia etc.), they should cease immediately and rest. If symptoms persist, further medical examination or referral to a specialist should be provided

Following an adverse event, a health and safety form report of the incident will be filled, and the competent authority/REC will be informed.

4.7 Data management

4.7.1 Data protection and anonymization compliance

The VITALISE project will take every measure to comply with the requirements and guidelines mentioned in the previous sections, particularly GDPR.

Data Management: All data will be pseudonymized during the life of the project and beyond. The master file containing the real identities of the participants will be encrypted in a password protected device and access will be restricted to the PI and the DPO of each Living Lab. Hard-copy documentation, if any, will be kept locked with restricted access.

Data Management Infrastructure: VITALISE has not selected up to this time (M6) a platform for cloud services to store and process the data which will be collected. The partners which will store data locally in their premises as well as the cloud service to be selected will fulfill all the following requirements:

- Data centers located in EEA or in country with active GDPR adequacy decision from the EC
- Security by default and by design
- Privacy by default and by design
- Ability to exercise personal data owner rights
- Regular and reliable back-up
- Ability to destruct data reliably, preferably following NIST 800-88
- Access control and management

Anonymization: Participants will be informed during the consent process that all research data collected during the project will be anonymized as soon as the obligations of the partners according to the GA are not affected. Data for which anonymization is not possible will not be disseminated. The anonymization procedures to be followed are detailed in Deliverable D1.4 section 5.

Concerns: Based on the aforementioned requirements for the cloud service and the data anonymization approach to be adopted, the level of concern is considered low.

4.7.2 Data exchange and access rights compliance

The VITALISE project will take every measure to comply with the requirements mentioned in Section 4.2. Thus, for ensuring compliance, specific roles of researchers and developers regarding data access and data exchange will be defined. The latter will be presented in detail in two deliverables of the project:

- D1.4 – Data Management Plan (M8): This will be the data management plan (DMP) concerning all datasets that are planned to be collected during the project. For each dataset, data sharing procedures will be defined (access type and access procedures) and partners activities and responsibilities will be established. The DMP will also report on the datasets or parts of datasets that will be publicly available in the context of the Open Research Data Pilot.
- D14.2 – POPD – Requirement No. 3 (M8): In this deliverable, among others, all the technical and organizational measures that will be implemented will be included. Additionally, a description of the security measures that will be implemented to prevent unauthorized access to personal data will be included. The deliverable will include the roles and access rights of each role.

In addition to the aforementioned deliverables, the Consortium Agreement of the VITALISE project and specifically Sections 8 and 9, has already established the partners' rights and obligations regarding the ownership and access rights to results (including the data generated).

Concerns: Based on the aforementioned, the level of concern for non-compliance with data access and exchange regulations is considered low.

4.7.3 Use of data in VITALISE deliverables and publications

With regard to the VITALISE Deliverables and publications, the consortium will comply with the guidelines provided in the Art. 29 of the VITALISE Grant Agreement of the project, regarding the use of data in the dissemination activities and more specifically, referring to:

Article 29.1: Obligation to public dissemination of results, incl. the obligation of, giving advance notice prior to a dissemination activity and the right of any beneficiary to object to it and the obligation of formal notification to the Commission before dissemination takes place (in case of no protection of the results);

Article 29.2: Provisioning of open access (free of charge online access for any user) to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results, (unless otherwise identified in the data management plan), the standard format of the bibliographic metadata;

Article 29.3: Provisioning of open access to research data generated in the action ('data');

while also ensuring the applicability of the standard ethical guidelines on data privacy and protection of personal data (see Article 27 - Protection of results, Article 36 - Confidentiality, Article 37 – Security related obligations and Article 39 - Processing of personal data).

In addition, the following guidance on data privacy regarding dissemination will be applied:

- Data are processed only for the purposes of the project on the legal basis of consent.
- All data to be disseminated (e.g., Publication, open-data repository etc.) must be made anonymous.
- Quantitative data will be disseminated in aggregate form.

- Excerpts may be included in any results section of any report or academic publication.
- Participants' anonymity must be respected and protected.
- Interview transcripts are not to be published in their entirety
- Video and audio recordings of persons must be anonymized and if this is not technically possible, they must not be disseminated
- The consortium should have a clear publication policy process outlined

Concerns: Based on the above the level of concern for non-compliance with good practices is considered low.

5 Ethics management and data control in VITALISE

A special role relating to the management of ethical and data protection issues in close coordination with the Ethical Board has been defined within the project:

Data controller (Leidy Vanessa Enriquez Florez, ENoLL): The data controller will monitor compliance with the guidelines and laws for a) the recruitment procedures, b) the processing of personal data, c) data transfers among partners, d) with Open Access and data sharing objectives of the Horizon 2020 framework.

Furthermore, the management of ethical and data protection issues during the VITALISE project will be performed according to the following actions/guidelines:

- This report is intended to be used as a reference manual for VITALISE partners regarding ethical, safety and data protection issues. The partners should consult this manual when designing components of the project or perform data processing.
- The agendas of the consortium meetings will include ethics and data protection to facilitate reporting of ethical matters and promote the discussion of relevant issues.
- The study protocols, consent forms and data transfer protocols should be disclosed to the Ethical Board and the Data Controller for a final quality check.
- A generic consent (Appendix I) form is to be used as the basis for compiling consent forms throughout the project
- Furthermore, if the need arises, the Data Controller is responsible for initiating contact with the Ethics Review Helpdesk of the EC and the European Data Protection Supervisor (EDPS), respectively.

The guidelines above are expected to support and ensure the compliance of the VITALISE activities, as well as the effective mitigation of issues that may arise during the rollout of the project.

6 Conclusions

From the beginning of VITALISE, the research activities and processes described in the GA have been, evaluated from an ethical, safety and data management viewpoint. The product of the evaluation is this First version of Ethics and Safety manual (Deliverable 1.2) which aims to define and report on the guidelines to be followed by the VITALISE project for its lifecycle and beyond. A review of relevant International, European and local legislation and guidelines is presented in the initial sections of the document. In Sections 4, the guidelines and policies to be followed during the VITALISE Joint Research Activities, Transnational Access, Open calls for researchers and Virtual Access are presented. Section 5 presents the Ethics management and data control actions and guidelines adopted by the consortium that will assist and monitor its compliance with the medical research regulations and guidelines. In addition, a thorough consent form template is included in Appendix I which will be used by all partners according to their specific protocols. It needs to be highlighted that this is a living document which will be regularly updated throughout the project leading to its final version (Deliverable 1.3) on M24.

7 References

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Appendices

Appendix 1 – Generic Consent Form

A generic consent form is presented below that will be translated and modified according to the needs of each VITALISE activity. The Consent form is split in two parts, the mandatory text and the optional depending on the protocol of the specific study undertaken by VITALISE.

CONSENT FORM
VITALISE
H2020 Grant No. 101007990

I the undersigned <name surname of participant>

Mandatory text

- I have been adequately and comprehensively informed by (name and position/area of responsibility of the researcher) for the purposes of the research in which I will participate and which is part of the research project VITALISE
- I have been adequately and comprehensively informed about the method and sources of the research financing.
- I have been adequately and comprehensively informed about what my participation in this research entails. In particular, I have been informed of all the rights and obligations I will have as a participant in the research.
- I have been adequately and comprehensively informed about any positive or directly negative, short-term or long-term consequence my participation in this research is expected to have concerning me or in relation with third parties.
- I have been adequately and comprehensively informed about how my personal data related to this research is processed and protected.
- I have been adequately and comprehensively informed about the provision and proper use of the medicines / devices / personal protective equipment /<other>/... (select accordingly) that I will use during my participation in this research.
- I am aware of the fact that my participation is voluntary and that I can withdraw my participation from the research at any time for any reason and without any impact on me.
- I know the Head of the research to whom I can address to withdraw my participation from this research or to notify any potential problem that might arise during my participation or after the completion of this research.
- No pressure was exerted to me, and I was given enough time to think and decide.

Optional text

- <In case of Incidental Findings, do you wish to be informed? If not, do you want a doctor of your choosing to be informed?> (Incidental Findings Policy added in information sheet)
 - I agree to be personally informed regarding incidental findings (YES/NO)
 - I agree to inform my doctor regarding incidental findings (YES/NO)
 - (If YES to the above) <doctor contact information>
- <Do you agree to the dissemination of the data collected?> (Data Dissemination Policy added in information sheet with explicit mentioning of a) all data will be anonymized before dissemination b) explanation of participant relinquishing control over the anonymized data c)

specific timeframe of anonymization d) the possibility of anonymized data being submitted to open-data repositories)

- I agree with the anonymization of my data and the subsequent submission of said data to open-data repositories (YES/NO)

- <Do you agree to be video/audio recorded?> (Add only if the video/audio recording is NOT necessary for the study. If it is necessary for the study, it is not an option)
 - I agree to be video/audio recorded (YES/NO)

- <Do you agree with being photographed/video/audio recorded for project dissemination purposes?>
 - I agree with photographs/video/audio of me be taken/recorded and be disseminated to public media (YES/NO)
 - (If YES to the above) I wish my face and other identifying characteristics to be blurred (YES/NO)

I consent to participate in the above research.

Participant's Signature: _____

Date: _____

day/month/year